

QUALITY INDICATORS OF ALTERNATIVE ROAD BITUMEN

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Abstract. *The article discusses the process of obtaining alternative road bitumen with high adhesion properties using a thermal oxidation experimental device based on gossypol resin, oil sludge, and diethanolamine waste. The results of "passive" adhesion of alternative road bitumen to mineral materials in the preparation of A-type asphalt mixture and the parameters of the limit angle of wetting were obtained. Then it was compared with road bitumen obtained from standard oil. The best indicator was the adhesion of the alternative bitumen on "passive" connection of 96%, and the limiting angle of wetting was 74 degrees. The obtained alternative road bitumen provides an opportunity to produce high-quality asphalt mixture according to the specifications.*

Keywords: *alternative road bitumen, oil sludge, gossypol resin, used diethanolamine waste, adhesion property, limiting angle of wetting.*

Introduction. It is known that today the need for road bitumen used in asphalt factories in the Republic of Uzbekistan is increasing day by day. Based on information from oil refineries and asphalt factories, there is not enough stock of raw materials to provide 100 percent of road bitumen for asphalt production.

According to experts, one of the main influencing factors of the long service life of asphalt-concrete road surfaces is the use of high-quality petroleum bitumen. Organic binding material, which meets not only the quality indicators set by the current state standard, but also the operational reliability requirements of asphalt-concrete road structural layers created with their use. The evolution of road construction development in countries with developed transport systems, including the European Union, the United States, Canada, led to the understanding of the feasibility of producing and using road bitumen from heavy, high-layer oils of a naphthenic base in the middle of the 20th century, and led to the emergence of regulatory requirements for them [1-3].

Analyzing the researches of scientists and researchers, many works were carried out on obtaining and developing road bitumen. In order to increase the amount of finished road bitumen and improve its quality, road bitumen compositions were obtained using rubber residues, polyethylene residues, oil and gas residues, oil industry residues and other modifiers [4-8].

Due to the shortage of bitumen, many types of construction and road bitumen are purchased in large quantities from neighboring countries. Due to the increasing need for bitumen, we have developed a new recipe of alternative road bitumen based on the secondary products of the local oil and gas and oil industry [9-10].

Relying on the information from the scientific works of the above researchers, the composition, physico-chemical properties, effects on humans and the environment of oil industry residue "Gossipol resin" and oil refining industry residue "Oil Sludge" are studied. The results were obtained and it was appropriate for us to use it as a raw material to obtain alternative road bitumen.

It was appropriate to obtain alternative road bitumen based on local residues by the scientific staff of the "Oil Chemistry" laboratory of the Institute of General and Inorganic

Chemistry of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. That is, on the basis of oil industry residue "Gossypol resin", oil refining industry residue "Oil sludge" and gas processing industry waste "Spent ethanolamine solution", work was carried out to improve the process of obtaining alternative road bitumen.

Research materials and methods. Selected raw materials and modifiers for obtaining alternative road bitumen:

As raw materials:

- the residue of the oil industry "Gossypol resin";
- the residue of the oil refining industry "Oil Sludge".

As a modifier:

- gas processing industry waste "Spent diethanolamine solution".

6 ready-made alternative road bitumen samples of 1 kg were taken using the thermal oxidation experimental device shown in Fig. 1.

1- oxidation reactor; 2- a mixer connected to an electric motor; 3- outlet of light components; 4- thermocouple; 5- thermocouple holding shell; 6- the place of obtaining ready-made alternative road bitumens; 7- absorbers; 8- reactor support; 9- air sending compressor; 10- electric heaters; 11- air intake valve; 12- heat measuring device.

Figure 1. An experimental device for obtaining alternative road bitumen

The process of obtaining 1 kg of ready-made alternative road bitumen. 750 g of primary purified and heated to 70°C gossypol resin is poured into thermooxidizing mixing reactor (1). Then 250 g of primary purified and heated to 70°C oil slurry is added to it and mixed for 5-10 minutes using a mixer (2) connected to an electric motor. The mixed mixture is oxidized with air using a compressor (9) for 4-6 hours after it is heated to a temperature of 200-250°C using heating elements (10) located in the reactor shell. Light components separated from the upper part of the reactor are cooled and condensed with the help of vapor-oil trap absorbers (7). Uncondensed light components are sent to the gas meter. 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 g of used diethanolamine solution prepared after primary purification was added as a modifier to the homogenous lump obtained as a result of oxidation and mixed, and 6 modified alternative road bitumen samples were taken from the bottom of the reactor. Using this experimental device, 6 alternative road bitumen samples were taken, and Table 1 includes their content ratios.

Table 1

Content ratios of alternative road bitumen samples

Name of samples	Composition ratios, % mass	
	Gossypol resin	Oil sludge
*AB-1	50	50
AB-2	60	40
AB-3	65	35
AB-4	70	30
AB-5	75	25
AB-6	80	20

*Note: AB - alternative bitumen.

In Table 1, asphalt mixtures were prepared to determine the quality of the samples (adhesion properties and limiting angle of wetting).

Asphalt mixture preparation technology [11] is carried out in the following order: 200±5 grams of small granite stones and granite gravel mixed with granite gravel and 10±1 grams of bitumen binder are prepared in two porcelain dishes. The dishes are kept in a thermostat at 130-140 °C for 20 minutes. The containers are removed from the thermostat and thoroughly mixed with bitumen binder until the surface of small granite stones is completely covered. Then the mixture is kept at room temperature for 20 minutes. Standard No. 025 or No. 05 metal grid, half of the mixture prepared in one of the vessels is placed on the grid in one plane and lowered into boiling distilled water. The same process is carried out with the second container of mineral-bitumen mixture. Samples of the mixture on grids are kept in boiling water for 30 minutes. During boiling, the bitumen released from the mixture to the water surface is removed using filter paper. After the boiling process, the grid is kept in cold water for 3-5 minutes, after which the mixture is taken on a filter paper and visually evaluated how much bitumen covers small granite stones.

Research results and discussion. It is one of the necessary factors for their mutual adhesion when wetting mineral material with bitumen. The classification of the wetting process is the limiting angle of wetting, which is determined by the slope of the limiting angle when a bitumen droplet makes contact with a solid surface.

The percentage of mineral materials covered with bitumen is included in Table 2.

Based on the results obtained in Table 2, it was determined that the percentage indicators of adhesion of the alternative road bitumen samples according to A-type "passive" connection are less than those of oil-derived BND 60/90 road bitumen. The limiting angle of wetting the glass base with bitumen is large. However, the sample AB-5 gave a much better performance than the rest of the samples, and it was recommended to use the used diethanolamine waste as a modifier to further increase its adhesion properties, and the following samples were taken in Table 3.

Table 2

Results on the adhesion of BND 60/90 and alternative road bitumen samples

Bitumen samples	Adhesion of type A - "passive" connection, in %	Limiting angle of wetting of glass base with bitumen (WGB), grad.
BND 60/90	78	111
AB-1	55	134
AB-2	58	127

AB-3	62	120
AB-4	67	116
AB-5	73	112
AB-6	71	115

Table 3

AB-5 sample composition and DEA ratios used

Sample name	Composition ratios, % mass		
	Gossypol resin	Oil sludge	Used DEA waste
AB-5M1	75	25	3
AB-5M2	75	25	5
AB-5M3	75	25	7
AB-5M4	75	25	9
AB-5M5	75	25	11
AB-5M6	75	25	13

Experimental test results were conducted to determine the wetting angle and adhesion properties of the samples presented in Table 3 and the obtained results were compared (Table 4).

Table 4

Quality indicators of BND 60/90, AB-5 sample and modified alternative road bitumen samples

Bitumen samples	Adhesion of type A - "passive" connection, in %	Limiting angle of wetting of glass base with bitumen (WGB), grad.
BND 60/90	78	111
without modifier AB-5	73	112
Modified with spent DEA waste		
AB-5M1	79	108
AB-5M2	86	93
AB-5M3	91	81
AB-5M4	96	74
AB-5M5	93	79
AB-5M6	92	83

In Table 4, sample AB-5M4 performed significantly better than sample AB-5 with petroleum BND 60/90 bitumen and no modifier.

Conclusion. It turned out that it was appropriate to take samples of alternative road bitumen with high adhesion properties using a thermal oxidation device based on gossypol resin, oil sludge and used diethanolamine waste. Its recipe for the production of alternative road bitumen, which gives an adhesion of 96% on "passive" coupling of A-type and a limiting angle of bitumen wetting of the glass base with bitumen of 74 degrees, is: gossypol resin-75%, oil slurry-25% and if the used diethanolamine waste is 9%, it is recommended to prepare a quality asphalt mixture and use it on highways.

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